

Trajnost digitalnih izdaj:
Uporaba statičnih spletnih strani na
portalu Zgodovina Slovenije - Slstory

Andrej Pančur
Inštitut za novejšo zgodovino
Ljubljana, Slovenija

JTDH2018

Oris predstavitve

- Uvod: trajnost digitalnih znanstvenih izdaj
- Moderne statične spletne strani
- Sistory TEI profil
- Konfiguracija in nadgradnja Sistory TEI profila
- Zaključek

Pomen digitalne trajnosti v humanistiki

- Trajno ohranjanje digitalnih podatkov: dodatno obdelani, vizualizirani, označeni, povezani in interpretirani objekti kulturne dediščine.
- Rezultati digitalno humanističnih raziskav:
 - raziskovalni podatki
 - prezentacija (npr. digitalna izdaja)
 - programska koda
- Izzivi glede trajnostne hrambe digitalnih izdaj:
 - specifične potrebe digitalno humanističnih projektov
 - omejena finančna sredstva
 - omejeni človeški viri in zanašanje na zunanje izvajalce
 - hiter razvoj novih spletnih tehnologij in standardov
- Alternativna rešitev za takšne izzive digitalno humanističnih projektov, ki slonijo na XML oz. TEI: moderne statične spletne strani

Moderne statične spletne strani

- “Nazaj v prihodnost!”
- Glavne pomanjkljivosti klasičnih statičnih spletnih strani: neposredno urejanje HTML kode, nezmožnost dinamičnega prikazovanja vsebine (npr. iskanje in povezovanje vsebine).
- Glavna pomanjkljivost dinamičnih spletnih strani: Rešitev (podatkovna baza, strežniški programski jezik, sistem za upravljanje vsebin) pogosto bolj zapletena kot dejanske potrebe uporabnikov.
- Prednosti modernih statičnih spletnih strani (zgolj HTML, CSS, JavaScript):
 - zmogljivost, gostovanje, varnost, vzdrževanje, kontrola verzij;
 - možnost dodajanja dinamične vsebine;
 - generatorji statičnih spletnih strani.

Pretvorbe XSLT za TEI dokumente: iz TEI v XHTML5

TEIC Stylesheets

```
graph RL; A[projektni profil] --> B[Sistory TEI profil]; B --> C[TEIC Stylesheets];
```

The diagram illustrates the process of converting TEI documents to XHTML5. It features three blue rounded rectangular boxes connected by arrows pointing from right to left. The rightmost box is labeled 'projektni profil'. An arrow points from it to a middle box labeled 'Sistory TEI profil'. A second arrow points from the middle box to the largest box on the left, labeled 'TEIC Stylesheets'.

Sistory TEI
profil

projektni profil

Slstory TEI profil

- Profil pretvornih programov XSLT konzorcija TEI (<http://oxgarage.tei-c.org/> in <https://github.com/TEIC/Stylesheets>):
 - parametri
 - XSLT spremenljivke in predloge
 - prazne (hook) predloge
- Slstory profil najprej namenjen objavljanju dokumentacije, nato digitalnih publikacij (monografije, zborniki, revije), danes tudi digitalnim znanstvenim izdajam.
- Ogrodje za odzivne uporabniške vmesnike ZURB Foundation.

Vključitev digitalnih izdaj v repozitorij portala Sistory: Handle identifikator, kontrola vsote (checksum), kompleksni digitalni objekti, metapodatki, OAI-PMH, API, RDFa

HOME / LITERATURA / MONOGRAFIJE

History of the Holocaust in Slovenia

Avtor(ji): Pančur, Andrej

Jezik: angleški

Vrsta gradiva: Besedilo

Vir: *Between the House of Habsburg and Tito, A Look at the Slovenian Past 1861-1980*

Leto: 2016

Založnik(i): Institute of Contemporary History

Soavtor(ji): Jurij Perovšek (ed.), Bojan Godeša (ed.)

Zbirka: Zbirka Vpogledi, ISSN 2350-5656; 14

Avtorske pravice:

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution Non-commercial Non-derivative 4.0 International license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/)

Trajna povezava: <http://hdl.handle.net/11686/36294>

[1] On 11 April 1945 the American Army liberated the German concentration camp of Buchenwald. The only fourteen-year-old Tamás Berthold Schwarz^[pers.] was among the surviving internees. Before he arrived to Buchenwald, in the end of January 1945 Tamás had barely survived the internees' "death march", whom the Nazi concentration camp guards had driven on as they retreated before the advancing Soviet Army. His father had been one of the unfortunate fatalities of this "death march". For months before that, Tamás and his fellow prisoners had suffered the impossible working conditions in the Jawischowitz (Polish: Jawiszowice) coal mine, a branch of the infamous Auschwitz concentration camp. Tamás had arrived there from Prekmurje already on 21 May 1944, together with his mother, younger sister and other members of his family. On his arrival to Auschwitz-Birkenau, Tamás had lied about his age, claiming to be sixteen years old. Therefore the Nazi doctor Josef Mengele^[pers.] sent him to work, while his mother and little sister died in the gas chamber immediately as "unfit for work".^[547]

[2] Mengele's^[pers.] decision was not intended to save Tamás's life, but only to exploit him as a labourer for the benefit of the German Reich. Had the Allied Coalition not ultimately defeated the Nazi Germany, Tamás would have sooner or later become a victim of the colossal Nazi destruction machine. All of this just because he was Jewish. During World War II the Nazi Germany, with eager assistance of its allies, managed to eradicate two thirds (between five and six million) of Jewish people from the occupied Nazi Europe. In comparison with the pre-war Jewish population, more than 70 % of Jews in Poland, the Baltic region, Czechoslovakia, Greece and the Netherlands died, and only slightly less in the Soviet Union and Yugoslavia. In contrast, in France, Bulgaria, Luxembourg and Italy around 20 % of the pre-war Jewish population died, which means that despite the severe persecution the majority lived to see the end of the war.^[548] The number of fatalities also differed considerably among Jews in Slovenia. While as much as 85 % of the pre-war Jewish population was killed in the Prekmurje region, in the other regions of Slovenia one fifth of Jews who had Yugoslav citizenship or had lived in this territory for a longer

```

<text>
  <front>
    <titlePage>
      <docTitle>
        <titlePart>Naslov</titlePart>
      </docTitle>
      <docAuthor>Avtor</docAuthor>
      <docEdition>Izdaja</docEdition>
      <docImprint>
        <pubPlace>Kraj izdaje</pubPlace>
        <docDate>Datum izdaje</docDate>
      </docImprint>
      <graphic url="url_do_slike.jpg"/>
    </titlePage>
    <div type="preface" xml:id="prf-01">
      <!-- Uvodna poglavja -->
    </div>
  </front>
  <body>
    <div type="chapter" xml:id="ch01">
      <!-- Poglavlja z glavno vsebino -->
    </div>
  </body>
</back>
  <div type="bibliogr" xml:id="bibl01">
    <!-- Bibliografije -->
  </div>
  <div type="appendix" xml:id="app01">
    <!-- Priloge -->
  </div>
  <div type="summary" xml:id="sum01">
    <!-- Povzetki -->
  </div>
</back>
</text>

```

```

<front>
  <divGen type="cip" xml:id="cip">
    <head>Kolofon CIP</head>
  </divGen>
  <divGen type="teiHeader" xml:id="teiHeader">
    <head>TEI kolofon</head>
  </divGen>
  <divGen type="toc" xml:id="id-toc">
    <head>Kazalo vsebine</head>
  </divGen>
  <divGen type="toc" xml:id="id-images">
    <head>Kazalo slik</head>
  </divGen>
  <divGen type="toc" xml:id="id-charts">
    <head>Kazalo grafikonov</head>
  </divGen>
  <divGen type="toc" xml:id="id-tables">
    <head>Kazalo tabel</head>
  </divGen>
  <divGen type="toc" xml:id="id-titleAuthor">
    <head>Kazalo vsebine, kjer izpiše še
      ime avtorja</head>
  </divGen>
  <divGen type="toc" xml:id="id-titleType">
    <head>Kazalo vsebine</head>
  </divGen>
  <divGen type="search" xml:id="search">
    <head>Iskalnik</head>
  </divGen>
</front>
  <back>
    <divGen type="index" xml:id="id-persons">
      <head>Seznam oseb</head>
    </divGen>
    <divGen type="index" xml:id="id-places">
      <head>Seznam krajev</head>
    </divGen>
    <divGen type="index" xml:id="id-organizations">
      <head>Seznam organizacij</head>
    </divGen>
  </back>

```


Konfiguracija Sistory profila

- TEI parametri:
 - splitLevel
 - documentationLanguage
- Sistory TEI profil parametri:
 - language-locale
 - za teiHeader

Projektna nadgradnja Sistory profila

- projektne nastavitve parametrov in spremenljivk, nove oziroma spremenjene predloge
- poleg osnovnega iskalnika (TipueSearch) možnost dodatnega dinamičnega prikazovanja vsebine:
 - DataTables
 - Highcharts
 - Google Maps
 - ImageViewer
 - Viewer.js
 - Saxon-JS
 - ...

npr. Kapelski pasijon

ents/moje/publikacije/kapelski/sistory.40000/para.html?type=page&mode=facs-dipl-crit&page=0r&lb=1

67%

Prvi koraki

Novo na ARRS

Išči

Sistory

Naslovnica

Kolofon

teiHeader

Kazalo

Uvodi

Prepisi

Vzporedni

Študiji

Priloga

Povzetka

Indeksa

Vaš iskalni niz

Vzporedni

Vzporedni prikazi faksimilov ter diplomatičnega in kritičnega prepisa:

Vrsta prikaza (strani)

Način vzporednega prikaza (facs-dipl-crit)

Prelom vrstice:

Da

Ne

stran 0r

>> 1

→ *Komödia*
od
Kristusoviga
Terplinja.

Katiro so nekidei na te
ueliki zhetertig inu
na te uelikonozhni
Pondelik
v Kappli spilali.

→ Komedija od
Kristusoviga trplinja, katiro
so nekidej na te veliki
četrtək inu na te
velikonočni pondelək v
Kapli špilali

Dostop, vzdrževanje in načrti

- <https://github.com/SIstory/Stylesheets>
- <https://github.com/SIstory/themes>
- <https://github.com/SIstory/publications>
- si4 repozitorij (METS aplikacijski profil) za nov SIDIH in SIstory